

TARA_	2022	06	06	PORT (CITY)	WALVIS BAY	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	06	09	WALVIS BAY	S	19	42.7	E	8	40.7	
End	2022	06	21	POINTE NOIRE	S	4	41.16	E	11	52.27	

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAING OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of this leg was to contribute to WP5 activities in the ATLANTECO project. These include several experiments aimed at understanding the effects of nutrients on marine microbiomes. Initially, we were meant to set up onboard co-limitation experiments in addition to the regular sampling undertaken during TARA cruises. However, this was deemed unfeasible due in part to issues related to acquisition of trace element clean samples and due to the faulty cable (which appeared to leach iron on deck). We then adjusted our objectives to continue sampling in line with the previous leg, aimed at sampling the microbiota along the Benguela upwelling region (Figure 1). In addition, we were meant to sample for microplastics in the Congo River. However, due to logistical constraints, this part of the expedition could not be undertaken. As a result, we established a 72-hour langragian experiment onboard TARA, following the fresh water plume from the Congo river (Figure 2).

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Samuel Audrain
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Leo
3	CREW - Mecano	Laurent ROGNIAUX
4	CREW - Deck	Mathew
5	CREW - Deck	
6	CREW - Cook	Carole
7	CREW - Media	Maeva
8	GUEST - Artist	Nicolas
9	GUEST - Observer	
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Guillaume Boudin
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Charlotte Begouen Demeaux, University of Maine
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Mancha Mabaso, University of Pretoria
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Douglas Couet, FR CNRS Tara
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Suzana
15	SCIENCE - F - Chief Scientist	Thulani Makhwanyane

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

We established eight discrete sampling stations for omics and nets. The stations were selected based on a previous paper which demonstrated a nutrient gradient off the coast of Namibia and Angola. We established a space for time sampling strategy, including a range of samples off the coast (Figure 1).

In addition, we undertook a 72-hour langragian experiment onboard. As part of this study, we aimed to investigate the effect of river plumes on the microbiome and followed the water mass outside Congolese jurisdiction water.

Figure 1 Sampling points onboard Lef 14 of the expedition from Namibia to Pointe Noire

Figure 2 Lagrangian study undertaken onboard the TARA off the coast of Congo

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

(describe how the objectives were achieved and highlight preliminary findings and observations)

We successfully sampled all eight stations and collected additional samples from the 72 hour experiment.

This was done in line with all the protocols planned following several unplanned events which led to to adjust our Sampling strategy. We are particularly pleased that, following the inability to enter the Congo River, the scientists And crew were able to plan a large experiment investigating the effects of river plumes on the South Atlantic.

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

(fill the table based on the sample IDs on the logsheets)

	Storage T°C	RT+10	RT+10	RT+10	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRG+4	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	FRZ-20	LN-80	LN-80	LN-80
	Box size	B-Box	G-box	XXL	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	W-box-S	W-box-M	W-box-L	Dewar #1	Dewar #2	Dewar #3
Protocol	Container type												
DGAS	ExeV-12mL						74						
DIC13	200-mL-Bottle		0										
DICTA	500-mL-bottle		35										
DO18	AmberV-40mL			4									
NUT-1	20mLCryoV						53						
SAL	125-mL Bottle			24									
DINO	60-mL-Bottle						34						
HG-M	125-mL Bottle			18									
HG-T	40-mL-Bottle			0									
MTE-T	60-mL-Bottle			12									
MTE-F	60-mL-Bottle			0									
MB320	4-mL-Vial							57					
MB023	4-mL-Vial							57					
MB<02	50-mL-falcon								57				
eDNA	sterivex								45				
NP550	20-mL-vial								27				
NP045	4-mL-Vial							27					
HG	Zip-lock	27											
PM	Zip-lock	33											
S320	5-mL-cryotube										74		
S023	5-mL-cryotube										74		
S<02	5-mL-cryotube							74					
P320	5-mL-cryotube										40		
P023	5-mL-cryotube										40		
HP	2-mL-cryotube											51	
SG	5-mL-cryotube										56		
FC	2-mL-cryotube												138
HC	2-mL-cryotube											84	
SEM	petri-slide	28											
FM20	50-mL-falcon				11								
E20	15-mL-falcon								11				
S20	5-mL-cryotube										11		

